

MID-TERM RECRUITMENT REPORT

Deliverable 2.13

Mid-term recruitment report

HIGH HORIZONS – D2.13

[GRANT NO. 101057843]

Deliverable Information	
Title	Mid-term recruitment report
Deliverable number	D2.13
WP number	WP2
Author(s)	Barbara Mouchtouri, Fani Kalala, Chara Bogogiannidou, Ioanna Voulgaridi, Christos Hadjichristodoulou
Lead beneficiary	UTH
Type	R: Document, report
Dissemination Level	PU: Public
Due date	28 February 2025

History of Changes	
Version 0.1	First draft of the report (3 February 2025)
Version 0.2	Draft reviewed internally (14 February 2025)
Version 0.3	Draft with integration of reviewers' comments (25 February 2025)
Version 1.0	Final draft (28 February 2025)

This document is issued within the frame and for the purpose of the HIGH Horizons project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Framework Programme under Grant Agreement number 101057843. Project partner LSHTM is funded by UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478. The opinions expressed and arguments employed herein do not necessarily reflect the official views of the European Commission or UKRI. The dissemination of this document reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission and UKRI are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. This deliverable is subject to final acceptance by the European Commission. This document and its content are the property of the HIGH Horizons Consortium. The content of all or parts of this document can be used and distributed provided that the HIGH Horizons project and the document are properly referenced. Each HIGH Horizons Partner may use this document in conformity with the HIGH Horizons Consortium Grant Agreement provisions.

Table of contents

Table of contents	3
List of tables	4
List of figures	5
Abbreviations	6
1 Introduction	7
2 Healthcare centres and personnel participating in recruitment	8
2.1 Sample size	8
2.2 Participating healthcare centres and collaborators	9
2.3 Research team.....	11
2.4 Laboratory staff.....	12
3 Methodology.....	12
3.1 Birth cohort timeline.....	12
3.2 Data collection tools	14
3.3 Biological specimens' collection	16
3.4 Laboratory infrastructure	16
3.5 Data management.....	18
4 Recruitment	22
4.1 Participants.....	22
4.2 Collected biological specimens.....	26
4.3 Completed questionnaires.....	26
4.4 Temperature measurements and logs	27
4.5 Incentives.....	28
4.6 Reported problems.....	28
5 Communications	29

6	Timeline	31
7	Reference	31
8	Annexes	32
8.1	Annex I: Team members involved.....	32
8.2	Annex II: Time points of data collection through questionnaires.....	33
8.3	Annex III: Time points of data collection through recording forms.....	34
8.4	Annex IV: GANTT chart for birth cohort study	35

List of tables

Table 1.	Participating healthcare centres, their capacities, and the corresponding dates of ethics approval or NDA signing	10
Table 2.	The number of participating obstetricians (N=62), paediatricians (N=6) and midwives (N=8) per city and healthcare centre.....	10
Table 3.	The list of the questionnaires and data recording forms.....	14
Table 4.	The timeline and type of biological specimens' collection from mothers, fathers, and newborns/infants.....	17
Table 5.	The total number of participating pregnant women (N=266), participating fathers (N=50), deliveries (N=62) and number of infants (N=63) per participating healthcare centre.....	23
Table 6.	The collected biological specimens derived from participating pregnant women/mothers, fathers and newborns/infants until 23 February 2025	26
Table 7.	Total number of completed questionnaires until 23 February 2025	27

List of figures

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of participating healthcare centres in Greece (as of February 2025).....	9
Figure 2. Timeline of the birth cohort study	13
Figure 3. Screenshot from REDCap software environment 'Add/Edit Records'	19
Figure 4. Screenshot from REDCap software environment 'Recruitment questionnaire'	20
Figure 5. Screenshot from REDCap software environment 'Record Status Dashboard (all records)'	21
Figure 6. Screenshot from REDCap software environment 'Record Home Page'	21
Figure 7. The weekly number of mothers and fathers' recruitments and deliveries (ISO-week 8,2024 – ISO-week 8, 2025).....	24
Figure 8. The cumulative frequency of mothers and fathers' recruitments, deliveries and current number of participating women (ISO-week 8,2024 – ISO-week 8, 2025).....	25
Figure 9. UTH's leaflet about the mother-child birth cohort	30
Figure 10. The timeline of questionnaires completion	33
Figure 11. The timeline of data recording forms completion	34
Figure 12. GANTT chart for Task 2.4	35

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
CHEQ	Cold and Heat Exposure Questionnaire
ERA5	5th European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts Reanalysis Product
EU	European Union
GAD7GR	General Anxiety Disorder-7 Greece
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
IT	Information Technology
NA	Not applicable
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
PHQ9GR	Patient Health Questionnaire-9 Greece
PHQ15GR	Patient Health Questionnaire-15 Greece
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
SOPs	Standard Operating Procedures
SQL	Structured Query Language
U/S	Ultrasound
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
UTH	University of Thessaly (Greece)

1 Introduction

The University of Thessaly (UTH) hopped on the HIGH Horizons project in April 2023 and leads Task 2. 4 “Prospective mother-child birth cohort study”. Under Task 2.4, a prospective mother-child birth-cohort study was designed with the aim to investigate the effects of heat exposure on maternal health during pregnancy, birth outcomes, and the health of children up to one year of age. The relationship between exposure including air pollution, thermal climate factors (temperature, humidity, wind and solar radiation), thermal physiological parameters such as core and skin temperatures rise, dehydration, thirst sensation, thermal sensation, heart rate, etc. and outcomes will be investigated, utilizing biomarkers and physiological parameters of effect and adjusting for important confounders. Adverse health outcomes for mother and child to be investigated include: birth outcomes (delivery method, birth weight, birth length, gestational age at birth, Apgar score, child's sex, head circumference, spontaneous abortion, congenital malformations, preterm delivery, stillbirth), child development and health, mother health, mother and child biomarkers and physiological parameters. The relationship of these parameters with both exposures and outcomes is expected to advance the knowledge on the interaction, confounding or effect modification of heat exposure and outcomes.

The study aims to recruit 500 pregnant women/child pairs from the participating Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology in healthcare centres and private clinics located in Greece. Women will be recruited at the 1st trimester of pregnancy and will be followed up for 12 months post-delivery. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first birth cohort study in Greece that examines the impacts of climate change on pregnancy, mother and child utilizing biomarkers. Moreover, it is the only study that investigates this correlation within the European Climate-Health Cluster. The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of UTH (Decision number 81/31.07.2023) and is published on Zenodo (Mouchtouri et al., 2024).¹

This document summarizes the mid-term recruitment progress of the prospective mother-child birth cohort study conducted by the UTH. Task preparations went well in accordance with the HIGH Horizons grant agreement. No major deviations from the initial plan were noted, however the recruitment itself had to be paused because of the extreme flooding in the Larissa region in September 2023. Pilot testing of recruitment started in February 2024 and until today, February 2025, 266 pregnant women have been recruited.

2 Healthcare centres and personnel participating in recruitment

2.1 Sample size

To calculate the sample size, power analysis was conducted by using the G*Power (version 3.1.9.7) software. For the purposes of the analysis, the 75th percentile of historical daily ambient temperature data was selected as a cut-off value to categorize participants to exposed and unexposed to heat. Indicatively, based on ERA5 temperature data from the city of Larissa (which is the largest urban centre in the area of the study) from 2019 to 2021, the cut-off would be approximately 29 °C. The outcome is defined as levels of specific biomarkers related to heat stress (cortisol, adrenaline, heat shock proteins, C-reactive protein, dehydration markers). As the sample size is also limited by other parameters (mainly the cost of laboratory analysis) and since multiple outcomes will be assessed, we performed a sensitivity analysis to determine the minimum effect size that can be identified with a sample size that can be supported by the available resources and capacity, in order to assess the feasibility of the investigations. By selecting a sample size of 400 pregnant women, a confidence level 95% and a study power of 80% an effect size of $d= 0.324$ can be identified, with assays of the t-test family. This lies between small and medium effect size according to Cohen criteria, practically indicating that the sample is sufficient to identify a minimum

difference of about a third of a standard deviation. Since the target for initial enrolment will be 550 persons, the sample is sufficient even if a proportion drops out.

2.2 Participating healthcare centres and collaborators

The healthcare centres, where pregnant women were recruited, are located in five Greek cities: Athens (the capital of Greece), Ioannina, Larisa, Volos, and Trikala (Figure 1). The study includes both public and private general healthcare centres, as well as private clinics for obstetric care with multiple centres participating in Athens, Larissa and Trikala cities. This approach contributes to the recruitment of pregnant women with various socioeconomic status. Healthcare centres specialized on pregnancy pathology have been excluded to minimize the selection bias.

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of participating healthcare centres in Greece (as of February 2025)

Table 1 provides an overview of the participating healthcare centres in each city, along with their capacities. Capacity is expressed as the ratio of the number of beds in the obstetrics departments to the total number of hospital beds. Ethical approval has either been obtained or is pending for each participating unit. All researchers, data collectors and collaborative doctors signed a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) to ensure protection of confidential information, as well as ethical and legal compliance with the project rules. Table 1 lists the ethics approval number and date, as well as the NDA signature date of collaborating doctors and clinics.

Table 1. Participating healthcare centres, their capacities, and the corresponding dates of ethics approval or NDA signing

City	Participating healthcare centres	Number of beds in the obstetrics department / Total hospital beds	Number and date of protocol ethics approval or signed NDAs
Athens	General Hospital "Alexandra"	82 / 440	
	University General Hospital "Attikon"	20 / 605	
	General Hospital "Elena Venizelou"	115 / 405	
	University General Hospital "Aretaio"	NA	ongoing
	Private obstetric practice (1)	NA	signed NDA
Ioannina	University General Hospital of Ioannina	46 / 850	
Larisa	General Hospital of Larisa	17 / 308	
	General University Hospital of Larisa	36 / 658	
	Private Maternity & Gynaecology clinic "IASO"	36 / 195	
	Private Maternity & Gynaecology clinic "Ygeia"	30 / 30	ongoing
	Private Maternity & Gynaecology clinic "Ippokratis"	20 / 20	ongoing
	Private obstetric practices (13)	NA	signed NDAs
Volos	Private obstetric practice (1)	NA	signed NDA
Trikala	General Hospital of Trikala	NA	ongoing
	Private obstetric practice (1)	NA	signed NDA

Table 2 presents the number of obstetricians, paediatricians and midwives participating in the birth cohort study network, per city and healthcare centre. Only obstetricians who have recruited at least one pregnant woman are included in the table. No distribution per healthcare centre was carried out for paediatricians, as they address the needs of birth cohorts across multiple sites.

Table 2. The number of participating obstetricians (N=62), paediatricians (N=6) and midwives (N=8) per city and healthcare centre

City	Obstetricians (N)	Paediatricians (N)	Midwives (N)	Participating healthcare centres	Obstetricians (N)	Midwives (N)
Athens	37	3	5	General Hospital "Alexandra"	17	2
				University General Hospital "Attikon"	5	1
				General Hospital "Elena Venizelou"	10	4
				University General Hospital "Aretaio"	2	1
				Private obstetric practice	1	1

City	Obstetricians (N)	Paediatricians (N)	Midwives (N)	Participating healthcare centres	Obstetricians (N)	Midwives (N)
Ioannina	4	1	1	University General Hospital of Ioannina	4	1
Larisa	19	2	2	General Hospital of Larisa	4	1
				General University Hospital of Larisa	6	1
				Private Maternity & Gynaecology Clinic "IASO"	4	2
				Private Maternity & Gynaecology Clinic "Ygeia"	5	2
				Private Maternity & Gynaecology Clinic "Ippokratis"	2	2
				Private obstetric practices	13	2
Volos	1	-	2	Private obstetric practice	1	2
Trikala	NA	-	1	General Hospital of Trikala	NA	1
	1	-	1	Private obstetric practice	1	1

Note: The same obstetrician or midwife may provide services at multiple healthcare centres in different cities.

2.3 Research team

The research team (see Annex I) comprises in addition to the project coordinator Professor Stanley Luchters, three senior level supervisors: Professor of Hygiene and Epidemiology Barbara Mouchtouri, Professor of Hygiene and Epidemiology Christos Hadjichristodoulou, and Professor of Medical Immunology Matthaïos Speletas. Five other members are also included: Associate Professor of Medical Immunology Fani Kalala, four researchers with medical background (Ioanna Voulgaridi, microbiologist, Spyros Topis and Evangelia Kontogiorgi, residents in obstetrics, and Zacharoula (Chara) Bogogiannidou, resident in paediatrics). The team is tasked with conducting the mother-child birth cohort study and coordinating the working group that performs the recruitments of study participants, sample collection and follow-up.

2.4 Laboratory staff

Laboratory staff consists of biochemists, biologists, and laboratory technicians (Annex I). The laboratory operates 24 hours a day, including weekends, to handle the collected samples, to perform their pre-analytical evaluation and processing, to ensure proper storage, and to conduct subsequent analysis. Also, laboratory staff is responsible for addressing the timely delivery of consumables to members of the obstetricians/midwives working group that recruits study participants and performs follow-up.

3 Methodology

3.1 Birth cohort timeline

Recruitment takes place around the 12th week (± 2 weeks) of pregnancy, followed by the first and second follow-up visits at the 22nd week (± 2 weeks) and 34th week (± 2 weeks) of pregnancy. Every woman at this stage of pregnancy who visits one of the participating healthcare centres is provided information about the study and if she wishes to participate in the study can be recruited. Monitoring continues at delivery, on the day of hospital mother-child's discharge, and during the first year of the infant's life (at 2 months, 6 months, and 12 months after delivery). At each of the previously mentioned reported time points, specially trained personnel perform data collection by conducting interviews, using questionnaires developed by the research team regarding participants' medical history, lifestyle, exposures to temperature and other environmental factors, and forms recording data from medical and laboratory examinations. The questionnaires are structured, and most interviews take place face-to-face, but there is also the possibility for online interview. In parallel, biological specimens are collected. Ad-hoc questionnaires, data recording forms and clinical samples are also collected whenever a medical event of interest (infections, fainting, surgery etc.) occurs. The timeline of the birth cohort study is presented in Figure 2 (A, B, C).

Figure 2. Timeline of the birth cohort study

Note. The timeline of data collection, data recording forms, biospecimens collection and U/S collection during pregnancy (A). The timeline of questionnaires, data recording forms, and biospecimens collection around delivery (B). The timeline of questionnaires, data recording forms, and biospecimens collection after delivery (C).

3.2 Data collection tools

The research team developed, in cooperation with experts in the field (including epidemiologists, obstetricians, paediatricians, environmentalists, a nutritionist, and a physiologist specialized in climate change and adjustment; Annex I), 25 questionnaires and 36 data recording forms. All questionnaires and data recording forms are presented below (Table 3). Moreover, Annex II and Annex III depict the time points when each questionnaire and data recording form is collected.

Table 3. The list of the questionnaires and data recording forms

Data collection tool
Questionnaires
Pregnancy recruitment questionnaire
Pregnancy follow-up questionnaire (2 nd trimester, 3 rd trimester, ad-hoc)
Father's questionnaire
House characteristics questionnaire of the pregnant woman
Psychometric test GAD7GR (Anxiety; General Anxiety Disorder-7 Greece)
Psychometric test PHQ9GR (Depression; Patient Health Questionnaire-9 Greece)
Psychometric test PHQ15GR (Patient Health Questionnaire-15 Greece)
Nutrition questionnaire of pregnant women, father
Cold and Heat Exposure Questionnaire (CHEQ)
Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure of the 2-month-old infant to high temperature
Questionnaire for the assessment of the exposure of the 6-month-old infant to high temperature
Questionnaire for the assessment of the exposure of the 12-month-old infant to high temperature
Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (1st trimester)
Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (2nd trimester)
Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (3rd trimester)
Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (before pregnancy)
Maternal exposure-participation assessment questionnaire in activities with exposure to high temperature (2 months post-delivery)
Maternal exposure-participation assessment questionnaire in activities with exposure to high temperature (6 months post-delivery)
Maternal exposure-participation assessment questionnaire in activities with exposure to high temperature (12 months post-delivery)
Maternal follow-up questionnaire - 2 months after delivery
Maternal follow-up questionnaire - 6 months after delivery
Maternal follow-up questionnaire - 12 months after delivery
Maternal follow-up questionnaire - Ad-hoc

Data collection tool
Data recording forms
PAP Smear results recording form
Vaginal swab results recording form
Complete blood count recording form
Biochemical test result recording form
Blood group testing recording form
Blood glucose curve recording form
Coagulation mechanism results recording form
Pathogens test result recording form
Haemoglobinopathy-enzyme disease screening recording form
Thrombophilia data recording form
Glycosylated haemoglobin screening recording form
Cystic fibrosis data recording form
Hormonal - immunological tests data recording form
Urine test result recording form
Nasopharyngeal swab data recording form
Saliva data recording form
Stool and gut microbiome test result recording form
First trimester ultrasound and biochemical markers recording form
Second trimester ultrasound recording form
Third trimester ultrasound recording form
Umbilical cord data recording form
Placenta data recording form
Colostrum and breast milk data recording form
Meconium data recording form
Guthrie card recording form
Pregnancy and delivery outcome recording form
Newborn characteristics recording form immediately after delivery
Newborn assessment record form in the 3rd 24 hours of life and somatometric data (including newborn psychometric development questionnaire and newborn food frequency questionnaire)
Two months old infant assessment recording form (including infant psychometric development questionnaire and infant food frequency questionnaire)
Six months old infant assessment recording form (including infant psychometric development questionnaire and infant food frequency questionnaire)
Twelve months old infant assessment recording form (including infant psychometric development questionnaire and infant food frequency questionnaire)
Maternal biomarker data recording form
Log sheet of child biomarker data
Infant vaccination coverage recording form
Hairs check data recording form

All questionnaires were pre-tested with subject-matter experts and one to two pregnant women and their husbands in January 2024. A pilot testing of the interview questionnaires and data recording forms was conducted in February–March 2024. Twenty-two out of the 35 recording forms were completed and registered as part of pilot testing. Minor issues were identified regarding the type of variables and the wording of questions, which were subsequently corrected.

A re-testing was then carried out, where a total of 13 recording forms with real data were entered (six records for the mother, four records for the father and three records for the child). A dashboard exists displaying all existing records/responses, and their corresponding status for every data collection tool.

3.3 Biological specimens' collection

According to the birth cohort study protocol, at specific time-points during pregnancy, at delivery and at specific time-points during post-delivery, biological specimens are collected from women, fathers and newborns/infants. The time-points and the type of collected specimens are presented in Table 4.

3.4 Laboratory infrastructure

The Laboratory of Hygiene and Epidemiology of the Medical School of the University of Thessaly is affiliated to the University General Hospital of Larissa and incorporates the Peripheral Public Health Laboratory for the Region of Thessaly and it is accredited in accordance to EAOT EN ISO/IEC 17025.

The research team developed standard operating procedures (SOPs) regarding the collection and management of the biological specimens, including a specialized placenta protocol. SOPs have been developed for questionnaires and specimen labelling where unique IDs are given in questionnaires, the specimen collection equipment and materials before the data and sample collection takes place. The team responsible for specimen handling is trained to apply sterile techniques.

Table 4. The timeline and type of biological specimens' collection from mothers, fathers, and newborns/infants

Participant	Pre-delivery			Delivery		Post-delivery		
	Recruitment (1 st trimester)	2 nd trimester	3 rd trimester	During delivery	Before discharge	2 nd post-delivery month	6 th post-delivery month	12 th post-delivery month
Mother	Whole blood & serum Urine Saliva Nasopharyngeal swab	Whole blood & serum Urine Hairs	Whole blood & serum Urine Faeces	Whole blood & serum Urine Vaginal swab Rectal swab Hairs Umbilical cord & blood Placenta Colostrum Nasopharyngeal swab Faeces Saliva	Breast milk	Whole blood & serum Urine Breast milk Faeces Saliva Rectal swab	Whole blood & serum Urine Breast milk Faeces Rectal swab Hairs	Whole blood & serum Urine Breast milk Faeces Rectal swab Hairs
Father	Whole blood & serum Urine Saliva Nasopharyngeal swab	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Newborn / Infant	-	-	-	Meconium Saliva Nasopharyngeal swab Dry blood spot Hairs Rectal swab Urine Whole blood & serum (voluntary)	Faeces	Urine Faeces Saliva Nasopharyngeal swab Rectal swab Whole blood & serum (voluntary)	Urine Faeces Saliva Nasopharyngeal swab Rectal swab Hairs Whole blood & serum (voluntary)	Urine Faeces Saliva Nasopharyngeal swab Rectal swab Hairs Whole blood & serum (voluntary)

Moreover, a Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology was purchased and is utilized exclusively for the birth cohort study to facilitate the identification and tracking of stored samples. The samples are stored at -80°C and a systematic monitoring and recording of their temperature is conducted. Forms for sample collection are completed, time of collection and time of delivery in the laboratory with details of conditions, quantities and other information is recorded in the forms, then RFID tracking for sample identification is used.

The laboratory maintains an alarm system and Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) to supply electricity power to freezers in case of power failure. An annual third-party audit is taking place for quality assurance in accordance with ISO standards. Regular checks and calibrations of equipment are taking place in accordance with ISO standards, while documents are maintained.

3.5 Data management

For the data management, the REDCap software was chosen that offers an easy-to-use and secure method of flexible yet robust data collection that meets HIPAA compliance standards. It is a secure web application for building and managing online surveys and databases.

Some screenshots from the REDCap software environment of the cohort are presented below (Figures 3 to 6).

The database and data management team is listed in Annex I.

Figure 3. Screenshot from REDCap software environment 'Add/Edit Records'

Add / Edit Records

You may view an existing record/response by selecting it from the drop-down lists below. To create a new record/response, type a new value in the text box below and hit Tab or Enter. To quickly find a record without using the drop-downs, the text box will auto-populate with existing record names as you begin to type in it, allowing you to select it.

NOTICE: This project is currently in Development status. **Real data should NOT be entered** until the project has been moved to Production status.

Total records: 13	
Choose an existing Record ID	Arm 1: Mother ▾ -- select record -- ▾
Enter a new or existing Record ID	Arm 1: Mother ▾ <input type="text"/>

Data Search	
Choose a field to search <small>(excludes multiple choice fields)</small>	All fields ▾
Search query <small>Begin typing to search the project data, then click an item in the list to navigate to that record.</small>	<input type="text"/>

[Create new records or edit/view existing ones](#)

Figure 4. Screenshot from REDCap software environment 'Recruitment questionnaire'

Q1M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εγκύου - ένταξη στη μελέτη

Data Access Group: Larissa hospitals

Editing existing Record ID 1005M.

Event: Recruitment (Arm 1: Mother)

Record ID 1005M
To rename the record, see the record action drop-down at top of the Record Home Page.

Ημερομηνία συμπλήρωσης ερωτηματολογίου
* must provide value
21-03-2024 Today D-M-Y

Ημερομηνία γέννησης
* must provide value
06-05-2003 Today D-M-Y

Κατοικία
 Αστική Αγροτική
reset

Περιφερειακή Ενότητα Θεσσαλίας **Πόλη/Χωριό** Λάρισα

Οδός Δράκοντος **Αριθμός** 18 **ΤΚ:** 41336

ΕΝΟΤΗΤΕΣ ΠΟΥ ΑΠΕΥΘΥΝΟΝΤΑΙ ΣΤΗΝ ΕΓΚΥΜΟΝΟΥΣΑ

Ενότητα 1 - Έμμηνος ρύσις

Q1M1.1 Πόσο χρονών ήσασταν όταν είχατε την πρώτη σας περίοδο;
12
Ετη

Q1M1.2 Πριν τη σύλληψη είχατε κύκλο 35 ημέρες ή λιγότερο;
 Ναι
 Όχι
reset

Q1M1.3 Πριν τη σύλληψη είχατε κύκλο μεγαλύτερο των 35 ημερών;

Example of Pregnancy questionnaire - Inclusion in the study

Figure 5. Screenshot from REDCap software environment 'Record Status Dashboard (all records)'

Record Status Dashboard (all records)

Displayed below is a table listing all existing records/responses and their status for every data collection instrument (and if longitudinal, for every event). You may click any of the colored buttons in the table to open a new tab/window in your browser to view that record on that particular data collection instrument. Please note that if your form-level user privileges are restricted for certain data collection instruments, you will only be able to view those instruments, and if you belong to a Data Access Group, you will only be able to view records that belong to your group.

Legend for status icons:
 Incomplete (no data saved) [?]
 Unverified (no data saved) [?]
 Complete (no data saved) [?]
 Many statuses (all same)
 Many statuses (mixed)

Dashboard displayed: [Default dashboard] [Create custom dashboard](#)

Displaying Data Access Group: -- ALL --

Displaying record: Page 1 of 1: "1005M" through "4002M" of 6 records ALL (6) records per page

Enter new record name for this arm: [+ Create](#)

Displaying: Instrument status only | [Lock status only](#) | [All status types](#)

Arm 1: Mother | Arm 2: Child | Arm 3: Father Table not displaying properly [?]

Record ID	Recruitment														
	Q1M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εγκύου - ένταξη στη μελέτη	Q4MC. Ερωτηματολόγιο οικίας της εγκύου	Q7M. Ψυχομετρική δοκιμασία GAD7GR	Q9M. Ψυχομετρική δοκιμασία PHQ15GR	Q11M. Ερωτηματολόγιο Διατροφής εγκύου, πατέρα	Q14M. Κλίμακα Έκθεσης στο Κρύο και τη Ζέση	Q18M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εκτίμησης έκθεσης-συμμετοχής της εγκύου σε δραστηριότητες με έκθεση σε υψηλή θερμοκρασία_1st_trimester	Q21M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εκτίμησης έκθεσης-συμμετοχής της εγκύου σε δραστηριότητες με έκθεση σε υψηλή θερμοκρασία_πριν_την_εγκυμοσύνη	D1M. Δελτίο καταγραφής αποτελεσμάτων TEST-PAP	D3MFC. Δελτίο καταγραφής αποτελεσμάτων γενικής αίματος	D4MFC. Δελτίο καταγραφής αποτελεσμάτων βιοχημικού ελέγχου	DSMFC. Δελτίο καταγραφής δεδομένων ομάδα αίματος	D7MC. Δελτίο καταγραφής αποτελεσμάτων μηχανισμού πήξης	D8MC. Δελτίο καταγραφής αποτελεσμάτων ελέγχου παθογόνων	D9MFC. Δελτίο καταγραφής ελέγχου αιμοσφαιρινοπαθειών-ερυθροκυττάρων
1005M	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
1006M	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
2002M	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
2500M	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
4001M	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
4002M	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●

[View data collection status of all records](#)

Figure 6. Screenshot from REDCap software environment 'Record Home Page'

Record Home Page

The grid below displays the form-by-form progress of data entered for the currently selected record. You may click on the colored status icons to access that form/event. If you wish, you may modify the events below by navigating to the [Define My Events](#) page.

[Choose action for record](#)

Record ID **1005M**
 Arm 1: Mother — Larissa hospitals Table not displaying properly [?]

Data Collection Instrument	Recruitment	Trimester 2	Trimester 3	Delivery	Discharge	Month 2	Month 6	Month 12	Ad Hoc
Q1M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εγκύου - ένταξη στη μελέτη	●								
Q2M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εγκύου - Παρακολούθηση (Follow-up)	●	●	●						●
Q4MC. Ερωτηματολόγιο οικίας της εγκύου	●	●	●						●
Q7M. Ψυχομετρική δοκιμασία GAD7GR	●	●	●						
Q8M. Ψυχομετρική δοκιμασία PHQ9GR	●	●	●			●	●	●	
Q9M. Ψυχομετρική δοκιμασία PHQ15GR	●	●	●			●	●	●	
Q11M. Ερωτηματολόγιο Διατροφής εγκύου, πατέρα	●	●	●			●	●	●	
Q14M. Κλίμακα Έκθεσης στο Κρύο και τη Ζέση	●	●	●						
Q18M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εκτίμησης έκθεσης-συμμετοχής της εγκύου σε δραστηριότητες με έκθεση σε υψηλή θερμοκρασία_1st_trimester	●								
Q19M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εκτίμησης έκθεσης-συμμετοχής της εγκύου σε δραστηριότητες με έκθεση σε υψηλή θερμοκρασία_2nd_trimester		●							
Q20M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εκτίμησης έκθεσης-συμμετοχής της εγκύου σε δραστηριότητες με έκθεση σε υψηλή θερμοκρασία_3rd_trimester			●						
Q21M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εκτίμησης έκθεσης-συμμετοχής της εγκύου σε δραστηριότητες με έκθεση σε υψηλή θερμοκρασία_πριν_την_εγκυμοσύνη	●								
Q22M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εκτίμησης έκθεσης-συμμετοχής της εγκύου σε δραστηριότητες με έκθεση σε υψηλή θερμοκρασία_2_μηνών						●			
Q23M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εκτίμησης έκθεσης-συμμετοχής της εγκύου σε δραστηριότητες με έκθεση σε υψηλή θερμοκρασία_6_μηνών							●		
Q24M. Ερωτηματολόγιο εκτίμησης έκθεσης-συμμετοχής της εγκύου σε δραστηριότητες με έκθεση σε υψηλή θερμοκρασία_12_μηνών								●	
Q25M. Ερωτηματολόγιο παρακολούθησης μητέρας - 2 μήνες κατόπιν τοκετού						●			
Q26M. Ερωτηματολόγιο παρακολούθησης μητέρας - 6 μήνες κατόπιν τοκετού							●		
Q27M. Ερωτηματολόγιο παρακολούθησης μητέρας - 12 μήνες κατόπιν τοκετού								●	
Q28M. Ερωτηματολόγιο παρακολούθησης μητέρας - Ad-hoc									●
D1M. Δελτίο καταγραφής αποτελεσμάτων TEST-PAP	●								●
D2M. Δελτίο καταγραφής δεδομένων καλλιέργειας κολπικού επιχρίσματος					●				●
D3MFC. Δελτίο καταγραφής αποτελεσμάτων γενικής αίματος	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●

[The grid displays the form-by-form progress of data entered for the currently selected record](#)

This software is not an open-source software and it is installed on a local web server which is physically located in the Computer Room of the Laboratory of Hygiene and Epidemiology of the University of Thessaly in Greece without any cross-border data transfer. Thus, the server is not virtual or cloud-based. The laboratory's IT staff does

installation, maintenance and support of this software. It runs on ubuntu operating system which is inside a Hyper-V Manager virtual machine environment. Installing this software had some requirements like installing some opensource software. Specifically, the Apache web server, the MySQL database server and the SMTP email server were installed. The database server is located behind the firewall. Each user has access to specific data and information. This software allows users who have been given full data export privileges, to export any and all data from their projects. Data may be exported in various ways and in various formats. Data may be exported as a CSV file from a report, in the form of a PDF file from the data entry page when viewing a particular record, and also in common statistical packages (SPSS, SAS, Stata, R). In addition, this software has many advanced features such as branching logic, file uploading, calculated fields, built-in project calendar and data-based triggers and alerts. There is a calendar application which allow us to add or modify calendar events and then view them either in a daily, weekly, or monthly format. Each questionnaire and data recording form consist of fields which have the following types: short text, number, date, radio buttons, checkboxes, yes-no, calculated field, paragraph text, file upload, dynamic query – SQL.

4 Recruitment

4.1 Participants

The recruitment started on February 22nd 2024 and the first pregnant woman was recruited in Larissa, Greece. The first 20 women were recruited in the context of pilot testing. The number of participants recruited as of 23 February 2025 is described below. The GANTT chart for the birth cohort study is presented in Annex IV. Until 23 February 2025, a total of 266 pregnant women, 50 fathers, 62 deliveries and 63 infants have been recruited/occurred. In Table 5, the number of pregnant women and fathers' recruitments, deliveries and number of infants per participating healthcare centre is presented.

Table 5. The total number of participating pregnant women (N=266), participating fathers (N=50), deliveries (N=62) and number of infants (N=63) per participating healthcare centre

City	Participating healthcare centres	Pregnant women	Fathers	Deliveries	Infants
Athens	General Hospital "Alexandra"	57	1	21	21
	University General Hospital "Attikon"	30	0	8	8
	General Hospital "Elena Venizelou"	62	6	1	2
	Private maternity practice	5	0	0	0
Ioannina	University General Hospital of Ioannina	19	0	9	9
Larisa	General Hospital of Larisa	46	24	18	18
	General University Hospital of Larisa	18	2	-	-
	Private Maternity practices and clinics	27	17	4	4
Volos	Private maternity practice	1	-	1	1
Trikala	Private maternity practice	1	-	-	-
TOTAL		266	50	62	63

The weekly number of recruitments and deliveries is presented in Figure 7 while the cumulative frequency is presented in Figure 8. From the total number of recruited pregnant women (N=266), 28 women dropped out (10.52%); 13 in Athens, 11 in Larisa, and four in Ioannina (Figures 7 and 8). Fifteen of 28 women (53.6%) did not specify the drop out reason (personal reasons), five (17.9%) women dropped out due to medical reasons, four women (14.3%) moved to an area away from the participating healthcare facilities, three women had limited available time and decided to drop out (10.7%), and one (3.6%) decided to be followed in a non-participating healthcare facility. From the total of 28 women, four (14.3%) dropped out around the time of recruitment, 16 (57.1%) before the 1st follow-up, two (7.1%) before the 2nd follow-up, one (3.6%) before the delivery, four (14.3%) before the 1st post-delivery follow-up and one (3.6%) before the 2nd post-delivery follow-up. Concerning the participating women (N=238) as of the present time, 30 (12.6%) women were at the 1st trimester, 70 (29.4%) at the 2nd trimester, 75 (31.5%) at the 3rd trimester, 58 (24.4%) post-delivery (23 (9.7%) at 0-2 months after delivery, 32 (13.4%) at 2-6 months after delivery and three (1.3%) at 6-12 months after delivery). Five (2.1%) terminated their pregnancy.

Figure 7. The weekly number of mothers and fathers' recruitments and deliveries (ISO-week 8,2024 – ISO-week 8, 2025)

Note: The ISO week date system is effectively a leap week calendar system that is part of the ISO 8601 date and time standard issued by the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO).

Figure 8. The cumulative frequency of mothers and fathers' recruitments, deliveries and current number of participating women (ISO-week 8,2024 – ISO-week 8, 2025)

4.2 Collected biological specimens

The total number of collected samples until 23 February 2025 is cited in Table 6. The number of collected samples represents the total count obtained through repeated sampling at different time points from each participant, excluding the father, for whom only a single sample was collected. The sampling of placenta includes umbilical cord and its membranes.

Table 6. The collected biological specimens derived from participating pregnant women/mothers, fathers and newborns/infants until 23 February 2025

Sample type	Mother	Father	Newborn/ infant	Total
Whole Blood (whole blood, serum, plasma etc.)	588	49	24	661
Cord Blood (whole blood, serum, plasma etc.)	48	NA	NA	48
Urine	577	49	33	659
Saliva	293	50	2	345
Nasopharyngeal swabs	334	48	55	437
Vaginal swabs	54	NA	NA	54
Rectal swabs	57	NA	48	105
Faeces	19	NA	6	25
Meconium	NA	NA	39	39
Hair	30	NA	19	49
Colostrum	23	NA	NA	23
Breast milk	12	NA	NA	12
Guthrie cards	NA	NA	43	43
Placental/umbilical cord tissue	58	NA	NA	58
Genetic material (DNA/RNA)	539	47	NA	586
Genetic material from placenta (DNA/RNA)	36	NA	NA	36

4.3 Completed questionnaires

Table 7 presents the total number of questionnaires that have been completed until 23 February 2025.

Table 7. Total number of completed questionnaires until 23 February 2025

Questionnaires	Number of completed questionnaires
Pregnancy recruitment questionnaire	266
Pregnancy follow-up questionnaire (2 nd trimester)	133
Pregnancy follow-up questionnaire (3 rd trimester)	58
Pregnancy follow-up questionnaire (ad-hoc)	3
Father's questionnaire	50
Home questionnaire of the pregnant woman	266
Psychometric test GAD7GR (Anxiety)	394
Psychometric test PHQ9GR (Depression)	38
Psychometric test PHQ15GR	394
Nutrition questionnaire of pregnant women, father	444
Cold and Heat Exposure Questionnaire (CHEQ)	394
Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure of the 2-month-old infant to high temperature	35
Questionnaire for the assessment of the exposure of the 6-month-old infant to high temperature	3
Questionnaire for the assessment of the exposure of the 12-month-old infant to high temperature	0
Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (1st trimester)	203
Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (2nd trimester)	133
Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (3rd trimester)	58
Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (before pregnancy)	266
Maternal exposure-participation assessment questionnaire in activities with exposure to high temperature (2 months post-delivery)	35
Maternal exposure-participation assessment questionnaire in activities with exposure to high temperature (6 months post-delivery)	3
Maternal exposure-participation assessment questionnaire in activities with exposure to high temperature (12 months post-delivery)	0
Maternal follow-up questionnaire - 2 months after delivery	35
Maternal follow-up questionnaire - 6 months after delivery	3
Maternal follow-up questionnaire - 12 months after delivery	0
Maternal follow-up questionnaire - Ad-hoc	0

4.4 Temperature measurements and logs

To measure the temperature to which the pregnant women are exposed, small i-buttons temperature data loggers have been provided to pregnant women to easily

monitor environmental temperature in any location. Three types of i-buttons are available: necklace, watch, and key-holder. Participants carry these i-buttons during all activities. During sleep, they are advised to keep the i-button in the same room. Totally, 84 women (31.6%) have received i-buttons and 3,100 days have been recorded.

4.5 Incentives

Study participants get an incentive. Instead of giving a financial compensation in cash or via a voucher, our team decided to give in-kind goods that are useful during pregnancy or after delivery.

Two companies were interested in providing us some goods, without further commitments from our side. Frezyderm S.A. offered 250 sets of baby care products. Additionally, KITE Hellas LTD offered 100 sets of breast care products including creams, organic pre-birth preparation oil sachets, compresses, and breast milk storage bags.

4.6 Reported problems

One of the primary challenges encountered by the mother-child birth cohort study has been the delay in its start caused by the "Daniel" and "Elias" storms. The critical infrastructure of our university was damaged and has not yet been fully restored. Moreover, during that period, the Laboratory of Hygiene and Epidemiology served also as the Coordination Centre for managing responses to public health issues.

Additionally, both mothers and fathers have demonstrated hesitation in committing to the study, largely due to its extended duration, the extensive nature of the questionnaires, and the biological sample collection. This has contributed to a recruitment rate lower than anticipated. A significant resistance has also been observed regarding the acceptance of i-buttons. To increase the possibility of i-buttons receipt, we now provide them in three different kind; as watch, as neckless or keyholder.

Beyond the lower-than-expected recruitment rate, participant retention has also been impacted by several factors, including time constraints and migration, leading to a number of dropouts.

It should be noted that recent amendments to the current legislation have altered the professional framework for medical doctors. Under the revised regulations, medical doctors employed in public hospitals are now permitted to offer private services, resulting in the transfer of a number of pregnant women to private practices.

In order to address the obstacles of the low recruitment rate, we are extending the participating healthcare centres and obstetricians' network. Moreover, paediatricians are included in the study and provide their services to babies in mothers' homes. To address hesitancy regarding participation in the study, efforts are being made to enhance its dissemination through formal channels while emphasizing its importance and significance.

Overall, it is expected that delays due to the 2023 floods will not affect the study expected outcomes. The only potential adverse outcome that might happen is to not be able to follow up a small number of children the 12 months after birth within the framework of the project. However, we have increased the numbers of recruitments and we expect that we will manage to achieve the target of 500 mother-child follow-ups within the project timeframe.

5 Communications

The mother-child birth cohort study has been featured in 11 dissemination events and highlighted in three articles in Greek media as of February 23, 2025.

A dedicated website for the study has also been developed and is accessible at <https://high-horizons.uth.gr/>. So far, the website has recorded 315 visitors, 410 unique page views and 13 downloads.

In total, six original posts have been shared on the LinkedIn and Facebook accounts of the Laboratory of Hygiene and Epidemiology at UTH, garnering 3 878 impressions on LinkedIn and 1 162 impressions on Facebook.

On April 11, 2024, an on-site dissemination event was held at the Laboratory of Hygiene and Epidemiology at UTH to showcase the study's progress and findings. Additionally, an informative leaflet about the study was created and distributed to all participating healthcare centres (Figure 9).

Figure 9. UTH's leaflet about the mother-child birth cohort

Τι προσφέρει η συγκεκριμένη μελέτη;

Ανώτερος σκοπός της μελέτης είναι η δημιουργία ενός συστήματος έγκαιρης προειδοποίησης (Early Warning System, EWS) για τις εγκύους και τα παιδιά τους. Επίσης, μέσω της δημιουργίας βιοτράπεζας, ενός χώρου δηλαδή συλλογής και αποθήκευσης βιολογικών δειγμάτων, στην οποία θα συμμετέχετε μόνο εφόσον επιθυμείτε, θα υπάρχει δυνατότητα για αναδρομική ανάλυση δειγμάτων και μελέτη παραγόντων που δύνανται να διαδραματίζουν σημαντικό ρόλο στην κύηση, σύμφωνα πάντα με τα ερωτήματα της επιστημονικής κοινότητας.

Γιατί να λάβω μέρος στη μελέτη;

Πέρα του ότι θα συμβάλετε στην εξέλιξη της γνώσης σε αυτό το επιστημονικό πεδίο, θα έχετε πρόσβαση σε όλα τα αποτελέσματά σας. Επίσης, η ομάδα μας απαρτίζεται από πολλούς Καθηγητές και Καθηγήτριες που θεωρούνται ειδικοί σε διάφορους επιστημονικούς τομείς και θα είναι στη διάθεσή σας εφόσον το ζητήσετε. Πριν αποφασίσετε εάν θέλετε να συμμετάσχετε στη μελέτη, μπορείτε να το συζητήσετε με το γυναικολόγο-μαιευτήρα σας ή να έρθετε απευθείας σε επικοινωνία με την ομάδα μας. Παρακάτω παρατίθενται τα στοιχεία επικοινωνίας μας.

Τρόποι επικοινωνίας

Για οποιαδήποτε επιπλέον πληροφορία, μην διστάσετε να επικοινωνήσετε μαζί μας με όποιο τρόπο από τους παρακάτω επιθυμείτε:

- αποστέλλοντας e-mail στο: high-horizons@uth.gr,
- καλώντας στο τηλέφωνο: 2410565054 (κα. Χατζήβρασιλείου Ελένη),
- επισκέπτοντας το χώρο του Εργαστηρίου Υγιεινής και Επιδημιολογίας του Τμήματος Ιατρικής, Παπακυριαζή 22, 41222, στην Πλατεία Ταχυδρομείου, Λάρισα.

Επίσης, μπορείτε να επισκεφθείτε το επίσημο προφίλ της ομάδας του HIGH Horizons στο Facebook [facebook.com/HIGHHorizonsEU](https://www.facebook.com/HIGHHorizonsEU) ή και να επισκεφθείτε τον επίσημο ιστότοπό μας high-horizons.uth.gr σκανάροντας το ακόλουθο QR code:

Μπορείτε και εσείς να συμβάλετε στη κατανόηση των παραγόντων που μπορούν να επηρεάσουν αρνητικά μια εγκυμοσύνη και να βοηθήσετε να προστατευτούν οι κύησεις του μέλλοντος.

Η συμμετοχή σου σήμερα, η προστασία της υγείας σας αύριο!

Το πρόγραμμα HIGH Horizons έχει λάβει χρηματοδότηση από το Horizon Framework Programme (Grant Agreement No. 101057843) της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης. Ο εταιρός LSHTM χρηματοδοτείται από το UKRI Innovate UK (αριθμός αναφοράς: 10038478).

Μελέτη για την επίδραση της υψηλής θερμοκρασίας στις εγκύους και στα βρέφη

Εργαστήριο Υγιεινής και Επιδημιολογίας
ΥΠΕΚΕ - Πανεπιστήμιο Θεσσαλίας

Τι θα χρειαστεί να κάνω εάν αποφασίσω να συμμετάσχω στη μελέτη;

Η συμμετοχή στη μελέτη είναι απολύτως εθελοντική και δεν σας επιβαρύνει με κανένα οικονομικό κόστος. Στο πλαίσιο της συμμετοχής σας στη μελέτη θα χρειαστεί να συμπληρώσετε ερωτηματολόγια, είτε δια ζώσης είτε διαδικτυακά, όπως εσείς επιθυμείτε, και να ληφθούν βιολογικά δείγματα. Επίσης, προκειμένου να πραγματοποιηθεί συσχέτιση της υψηλής θερμοκρασίας με την έκβαση της κύησης, θα σας ζητηθεί να φοράτε ή να κουβαλάτε ένα αξεσουάρ μαζί σας (ρολόι ή μεταξόν ή μπραβόκι) το οποίο θα καταγράφει τη θερμοκρασία του περιβάλλοντος στο οποίο θα εκτίθεστε.

Διασφαλίζονται τα προσωπικά δεδομένα όλων των συμμετεχουσών/συμμετεχόντων;

Το πρωτόκολλο έχει εγκριθεί από την Επιτροπή Ηθικής και Δεοντολογίας του Πανεπιστημίου Θεσσαλίας. Η έρευνα διεξάγεται πάντα έχοντας διασφαλίσει την προστασία των προσωπικών σας δεδομένων, σύμφωνα πάντα με τον κανονισμό ηθικής και δεοντολογίας. Μπορείτε να αποχωρήσετε από τη μελέτη οποιαδήποτε στιγμή και τα δεδομένα σας θα διαγραφούν/καταστραφούν.

Ποιο είναι το πλαίσιο μελέτης και ποιοι φορείς συμμετέχουν σε αυτήν;

Η συγκεκριμένη μελέτη διεξάγεται στο πλαίσιο ενός μεγάλου ευρωπαϊκού ερευνητικού προγράμματος HIGH Horizons (Heat Indicators for Global Health Monitoring) που επικεντρώνεται στις εγκύους, τα έμβρυα και τα βρέφη τους. Στη μελέτη συμμετέχουν το Τμήμα Ιατρικής του Πανεπιστημίου Θεσσαλίας, ο Παγκόσμιος Οργανισμός Υγείας (ΠΟΥ) και Πανεπιστήμια της Ευρώπης και της Αφρικής. Σκοπός της μελέτης είναι να κατανοήσουμε πώς η υψηλή θερμοκρασία επηρεάζει άμεσα ή/και έμμεσα την υγεία των εγκύων και των παιδιών τους.

Τι γνωρίζουμε μέχρι σήμερα;

Μέχρι σήμερα έχει παρατηρηθεί ότι η έκθεση των εγκύων σε υψηλές θερμοκρασίες μπορεί να έχει αρνητικές επιπτώσεις στην πορεία της εγκυμοσύνης τους. Ωστόσο, προς το παρόν, δεν έχουν αποσαφηνιστεί ποια είναι τα ασφαλή όρια της έκθεσης και με ποιους μηχανισμούς ανταποκρίνεται ο ανθρώπινος οργανισμός της εγκύου στις υψηλές θερμοκρασίες. Επίσης, δεν έχουν ορθοτοποιηθεί οι παράμετροι οι οποίες θα μπορούσαν να χρησιμοποιηθούν ως προγνωστικοί δείκτες για την εξέλιξη της εγκυμοσύνης.

Ποια/ποιοι μπορεί να λάβει μέρος στη μελέτη;

Μπορεί να συμμετάσχει οποιαδήποτε έγκυος γυναίκα επιθυμεί, βρίσκεται κοντά στην 12η εβδομάδα της κύησης της και διαμένει στη περιοχή της Θεσσαλίας, της Αττικής, της Θεσσαλονίκης, των Ιωνανών ή στην Κύπρο. Η συμμετοχή της εγκύου συνεπάγεται και τη συμμετοχή/παρακολούθηση του εμβρύου της και μετέπειτα, του βρέφους της (μέχρι την ολοκλήρωση του πρώτους έτους ζωής του). Στη μελέτη μπορεί να συμμετάσχει, εφόσον επιθυμεί, και ο πατέρας του παιδιού.

6 Timeline

Until the end of the cohort (August 2026) we are planning to enrol the expected number of 500 recruited pregnant women:

- Pregnant women recruited until February 2026 will be monitored throughout their entire pregnancy. We believe in reaching our goal of 500 participants, as 266 women have already been enrolled.
- Woman-infant pairs that were recruited up to February 2025 will be monitored for the whole of the study, including 12 months post-delivery.
- Within the following three months, we are going to analyse the clinical and environmental data for the first 50 deliveries.
- We are going to prepare a draft publication plan which will include the birth cohort protocol, descriptive analysis of data collected so far and planning for additional publications reporting laboratory results associated with birth outcomes.

7 Reference

¹ Mouchtouri V, Koureas M, Kyritsi M, Kalala F, Speletas M, Hadjichristodoulou C, et al. HIGH Horizons - Study Initiation Package for the prospective mother-child birth cohort study of the effect of heat exposure on health, Greece. Zenodo; 2024 Jul. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12759714>

8 Annexes

8.1 Annex I: Team members involved

Research team
Barbara Mouchtouri
Christos Hadjichristodoulou
Matthaios Speletas
Fani Kalala
Ioanna Voulgaridi
Zacharoula Bogogiannidou
Spiridon Topis
Evangelia Kontogiorgi
Georgios Papageorgas Chrelas
Stanley Luchters
Experts in different fields
Andreas Flouris
Vana (Vasiliki) Papaevangelou
Androniki Naska
Vasiliki Benetou
Jørn Toftum
Messinis Ioannis
Laboratory team
Evangelia Vachtsioli
Alexia Matziri
Konstantina Kola
Database and data management team
Evangelos Kokkalis
Eleni Hatzivasileiou
Garyfallia Stefanou
George Gounelas
Emmanouil Tsolias
Foivi Markotsi

8.2 Annex II: Time points of data collection through questionnaires

Figure 10. The timeline of questionnaires completion

<u>Questionnaires</u>		Recruitment	Trimester 2	Trimester 3	Delivery	Discharge	Month 2	Month 6	Month 12	Ad hoc
1	Pregnancy recruitment questionnaire	M								
2	Pregnancy follow-up questionnaire - ad-hoc									M
3	Pregnancy follow-up questionnaire – 2nd trimester		M							
4	Pregnancy follow-up questionnaire – 3rd trimester			M						
5	Father's questionnaire	F								
6	Home questionnaire of the pregnant woman	M								
7	Psychometric test GAD7GR (Anxiety)	M	M	M						
8	Psychometric test PHQ9GR (Depression)						M	M	M	
9	Psychometric test PHQ15GR	M	M	M			M	M	M	
10	Nutrition questionnaire of pregnant women, father	M	F	M	M		M?	M?	M?	
11	Cold and Heat Exposure Questionnaire (CHEQ)	M	M	M						
12	Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure of the 2-month-old infant to high temperature						C			
13	Questionnaire for the assessment of the exposure of the 6-month-old infant to high temperature							C		
14	Questionnaire for the assessment of the exposure of the 12-month-old infant to high temperature								C	
15	Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (1st trimester)	M								
16	Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (2nd trimester)		M							
17	Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (3rd trimester)			M						
18	Questionnaire for the assessment of exposure-participation of pregnant women in activities with exposure to high temperature (before pregnancy)	M								
19	Maternal exposure-participation assessment questionnaire in activities with exposure to high temperature (2 months post-delivery)						M			
20	Maternal exposure-participation assessment questionnaire in activities with exposure to high temperature (6 months post-delivery)							M		
21	Maternal exposure-participation assessment questionnaire in activities with exposure to high temperature (12 months post-delivery)								M	
22	Maternal follow-up questionnaire - 2 months after delivery									
23	Maternal follow-up questionnaire - 6 months after delivery						M			
24	Maternal follow-up questionnaire - 12 months after delivery							M		
25	Maternal follow-up questionnaire - Ad-hoc									M

Note:

- GAD7GR: General Anxiety Disorder-7 Greece
- PHQ9GR: Patient Health Questionnaire-9 Greece
- PHQ15GR: Patient Health Questionnaire-15 Greece
- M: mother
- F: father
- C: child

8.3 Annex III: Time points of data collection through recording forms

Figure 11. The timeline of data recording forms completion

Data recording forms		Recruitment	Trimester 2	Trimester 3	Delivery	Discharge	Month 2	Month 6	Month 12	Ad hoc			
1	TEST-PAP results recording form	M								M			
2	Vaginal swab results recording form				M			M		M			
3	Complete blood count recording form	M	F	M	M		M	C	M	C	M	C	M, F, C
4	Biochemical test result recording form	M	F	M	M	C	M	C	M	C	M	C	M, F, C
5	Blood group testing recording form	M	F		C								
6	Blood glucose curve recording form		M	M									
7	Coagulation mechanism results recording form	M	M	M									M, C
8	Pathogens test result recording form	M		M									M, C
9	Haemoglobinopathy-enzyme disease screening recording form	M	F										C
10	Thrombophilia data recording form	M	F										C
11	Glycosylated haemoglobin screening recording form	M											M
12	Cystic fibrosis data recording form	M	F										C
13	Hormonal - immunological tests data recording form	M					M						M, C
14	Urine test result recording form	M	F	M	M	C	M	C	M	C	M	C	M, F, C
15	Nasopharyngeal swab data recording form	M	F		M	C	M	C	C	C	M	C	
16	Saliva data recording form	M	F		M	C	M	C	C	C	C	C	
17	Stool and gut microbiome test result recording form			M	M	C	M	C	M	C	M	C	
18	First trimester ultrasound and biochemical markers recording form	M											
19	Second trimester ultrasound recording form		M										
20	Third trimester ultrasound recording form			M									
21	Umbilical cord data recording form				M - C								
22	Placenta data recording form				M								
23	Colostrum and breast milk data recording form				M	M	M	M	M				
24	Meconium data recording form				C								
25	Guthrie card recording form					C							
26	Pregnancy and delivery outcome recording form				M	C							
27	Newborn characteristics recording form immediately after delivery				C								
28	Newborn assessment record form in the 3rd 24 hours of life and somatometric data (including newborn psychometric development questionnaire and newborn food frequency questionnaire)					C							
29	Two months old infant assessment recording form (including infant psychometric development questionnaire and infant food frequency questionnaire)						C						
30	Six months old infant assessment recording form (including infant psychometric development questionnaire and infant food frequency questionnaire)							C					
31	Twelve months old infant assessment recording form (including infant psychometric development questionnaire and infant food frequency questionnaire)								C				
32	Maternal biomarker data recording form	M	M	M	M		M	M	M	M			M
33	Child biomarker data recording form				C	(C)	C	C	C	C			C
34	Infant vaccination coverage recording form						C	C	C	C			
35	Hairs check data recording form		M		M	C		M	C	M	C		

Note: M: mother; F: father; C: child

8.4 Annex IV: GANTT chart for birth cohort study

Figure 12. GANTT chart for Task 2.4

HIGH HORIZONS – D2.13 (Gantt Chart and Progress)

Current Date: 24/2/2025

Select a period to highlight at right. A legend describing the charting follows.

Note: Last update of the GANTT chart was made on 24 February 2025.